

SHORT NOTES

SEARCH FOR NEW INSECTICIDES

BY S. S. TIWARI AND BRAJENDRA NATH TRIPATHI

The synthesis of various 2-allyloxy- and 2-*o*-chlorobenzoyloxy-4:5-dimethylphenyl alkyl ketones, and of 2-allyloxy-4:6-dimethyl α -furophenone as potent contact insecticides containing allyl or *ortho*-chlorobenzyl groups as toxophore and ether and ketonic linkages as lipoid solubilising groups, has been described previously (*this Journal*, 1954, 31, 76; 1956, 33, 214). This communication describes their insecticidal activity in terms of 50% and 100% knock-down of common house-flies.

All these compounds are mildly active. Only 2-*o*-chlorobenzoyloxy-4:5-dimethyl propiophenone and 2-allyloxy-4:6-dimethyl α -furophenone have been found to be more active knock-down compounds as compared to D.D.T. and B.H.C. It appears that the activity of 2-allyloxy-4:6-dimethyl α -furophenone owes much to the presence of α -furoyl group rather than to allyloxy group, as many α -furoyl compounds have been reported to be good contact insecticides (Gilman and Hewett, *Iowa State Col. J. Sci.*, 1932, 6, 439; 1933, 7, 419).

Bioassay of Insecticidal Action.—The testing of the insecticidal activity has been done exclusively against 5 days old and laboratory-bred common house-flies, obtained from regular test-fly colony reared for biological standardisation.

The various compounds were first diluted in mineral turpentine to 1% (w/v) strength; 0.2 c.c. of the solutions, so obtained, was sprayed by means of an aero spray gun at a predetermined pressure into glass jars, standing on a revolving table, covered by mosquito netting and containing 20 test-flies per test. Each test was carried in duplicate. The periods required to ensure the dorsal position of 50% and 100% of the flies exposed to the insecticidal spray were recorded. In one instance, when a slow insecticidal activity was noticed, the percentage of knock-down for 60 minutes was recorded. The results given here are the average of the two experiments. In the control experiments, *i.e.* spraying of the flies with solvent alone did not exhibit any mortality within the time of observation.

For the sake of comparison of the insecticidal activity of the compounds with standard insecticides, the results under the same conditions of the experiments have also been recorded with the following:

- (a) 2:2-bis-(4'-chlorophenyl)-1,1:1-trichloroethane or D.D.T. (1% solution).
- (b) Hexachlorocyclohexane or B.H.C. (having 13% γ -isomer, 1% solution).
- (c) Pyrethrin I & II (0.02% solution).

During the testing time the temperature remained 28° to 30° and the relative humidity 76% to 83%.

TABLE I

[A = 2-Allyloxy-4:5-dimethyl-. B = 2-o-Chlorobenzoyloxy-4:5-dimethyl-].

No.	Compound.	Knock down.		No.	Compound.	Knock down.	
		50%.	100%.			50%	100%
1.	A acetophenone	30.5 min	45.0 min	9.	B-butyrophenone	16.5	37.5
2.	A-propiofenone	43.5	60.0	10.	B-caprophenone	11.5	19.5
3.	A-butyrophenone	27.0	45.5	11.	B-heptophenone	21.0	53.5
4.	A-caprophenone	16.0	22.0	12.	B-caprylophenone	16.5	47.5
5.	A-heptophenone	19.0	33.5	13.	2-Allyloxy-4:6'-dime- thyl-ferophenone	3.5	9.0
6.	A-caprylophenone	13.0	24.5		D.D.T.	5.5	9.5
7.	B-acetophenone 40% K' D in bomins.				B.H.C.	5.0	7.0
8.	B-propiofenone	3.0	7.5		Pyrethrin I & II	14.3	34.3

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ON THE REACTION OF DIETHYLAMINE WITH A SATURATED AQUEOUS SOLUTION OF ANTIMONY TRICHLORIDE

BY S. MOHAPATRA AND CH. B. NANDA

Secondary amines have got very little tendency to function as a donor molecule. It was therefore thought worthwhile to study the reaction of an aliphatic secondary amine with a saturated aqueous solution of antimony trichloride. The results of the investigation with diethylamine are recorded herein.

Pure chemicals were used. A saturated aqueous solution of antimony trichloride was cooled in ice and an ice-cold sample of diethylamine was added dropwise with stirring. The addition of an excess of the latter reagent was avoided. Much heat was produced and a white solid was obtained. It was filtered through a sintered glass crucible and repeatedly washed with ether till free from antimony trichloride. It was dried in vacuum over concentrated sulphuric acid for over 72 hours.

Like the compound obtained with dioxan (*this Journal*, 1956, 33, 532) it is easily hydrolysed by water and an aqueous extract gives the test of antimony. It is soluble in hydrochloric acid and reacts with a solution of sodium hydroxide affording a clear solution and ammonia. It melts at 90° with decomposition and liberation of ammonia.

Analysis.—Antimony, chlorine and nitrogen contents were estimated as done in the pyridine compound (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 538). The mean value of four different samples analysed are: Sb 38.40%, chlorine 33.80%, and nitrogen 4.54% and those calculated for $(C_2H_5)_2NH.SbCl_3.H_2O$ are 38.15%, 33.35% and 4.38% respectively. The corresponding amount of diethylamine calculated from the nitrogen content is 22.84%. If water content is taken as the difference of the sum of the percentages of Sb, Cl and $(C_2H_5)_2NH$ from hundred, it comes out to be 5.66% (calculated for the above compound is 5.63%).

The compound is most probably a salt of the type obtained with dioxan (*loc. cit.*, p. 532) and may be represented by

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
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